

Supplementary Information

Supplementary table 1. Number of little penguins and type of loggers deployed for each year and breeding stage. (Females/Males)

		Season										
		2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Breeding stage	Incubation	0	16 (5/11)	16 (8/8)	9 (5/4)	26 (12/14)	23 (7/16)	21 (12/9)	28 (20/8)	30 (14/16)	24 (10/14)	15 (8/7)
	Guard	28 (13/15)	18 (10/8)	9 (4/5)	10 (5/5)	19 (9/10)	16 (9/7)	13 (5/8)	13 (7/6)	17 (7/10)	17 (8/9)	18 (10/8)
	Post-guard	7 (3/4)	19 (12/7)	16 (9/7)	4 (4/0)	12 (7/5)	11 (6/5)	12 (7/5)	19 (12/7)	16 (8/8)	9 (2/7)	12 (9/3)
Logger type		CatTrack					CatTrack and AxyTrack		CatTrack		AxyTrack	

Supplementary table 2. Model selection for (A) Daily number of spectators (n = 1342), (B) Daily number of vessels (n = 824), (C) Overlap among penguins (n = 110), (D) Overlap between penguins and marine traffic (n = 49), (E) Departure time relative to nautical dawn (n = 21), (F) Arrival time relative to nautical dusk (n = 21), (G) Mass gain per day at sea (n = 21), (H) Chick meal size (n = 14).

(A)

month	year	<i>df</i>	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
+	+	15	-10,411.41	20,853.18	0.00	1.00
	+	12	-10,599.91	21,224.05	370.87	0.00
+		5	-10,809.75	21,629.54	776.36	0.00
		2	-10,920.32	21,844.65	991.46	0.00

(B)

month	year	<i>df</i>	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
+	+	11	-4,677.40	9,377.13	0.00	1.00
	+	8	-4,706.24	9,428.66	51.53	0.00
+		5	-4,722.13	9,454.33	77.20	0.00
		2	-4,747.70	9,499.41	122.28	0.00

(C)

Year_A	Year_B	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
+	+	22	24.25	7.14	0.00	1.00
+		12	-0.64	28.49	21.35	0.00
	+	12	-0.64	28.49	21.35	0.00
		2	-15.50	35.12	27.98	0.00

(D)

boat_year	penguin_year	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
	+	8	89.82	-160.05	0.00	1.00
+	+	14	93.95	-147.55	12.50	0.00
		2	20.95	-37.63	122.42	0.00
+		8	21.39	-23.17	136.88	0.00

(E)

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
+				4	-74.65	159.81	0.00	0.70
+		-1.50		5	-74.47	162.94	3.13	0.15
+	1.17			5	-74.62	163.23	3.42	0.13
+	2.25	-1.93		6	-74.34	166.68	6.87	0.02
+			+	10	-68.09	178.18	18.37	0.00
+		-7.94	+	11	-67.65	186.63	26.82	0.00
+	-4.54		+	11	-67.95	187.24	27.43	0.00
				2	-92.46	189.59	29.78	0.00
	-2.94			3	-92.42	192.24	32.43	0.00
		-1.55		3	-92.43	192.26	32.45	0.00

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
	-2.30	-1.09		4	-92.40	195.30	35.49	0.00
+	0.04	-7.96	+	12	-67.65	198.30	38.49	0.00
			+	8	-91.53	211.05	51.24	0.00
	-29.13		+	9	-90.71	215.79	55.98	0.00
		-5.92	+	9	-91.48	217.33	57.52	0.00
	-42.81	17.81	+	10	-90.46	222.91	63.10	0.00

(F)

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
				2	-78.57	161.81	0.00	0.53
		-1.34		3	-78.46	164.34	2.53	0.15
	1.64			3	-78.52	164.45	2.64	0.14
			+	8	-69.12	166.25	4.44	0.06
+				4	-77.96	166.42	4.61	0.05
	2.74	-1.88		4	-78.33	167.16	5.35	0.04
+		-1.68		5	-77.79	169.57	7.76	0.01
+	1.57			5	-77.91	169.82	8.01	0.01
	7.59		+	9	-68.75	171.86	10.05	0.00
		-3.00	+	9	-69.02	172.40	10.59	0.00

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
+	2.78	-2.19		6	-77.64	173.28	11.47	0.00
+			+	10	-67.55	177.10	15.29	0.00
	15.97	-10.23	+	10	-67.92	177.84	16.04	0.00
+		-11.66	+	11	-66.47	184.28	22.47	0.00
+	8.72		+	11	-67.10	185.54	23.73	0.00
+	19.56	-19.85	+	12	-64.39	191.78	29.97	0.00

(G)

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
+	-56.86			5	-101.14	216.28	0.00	0.74
+	-50.32	-10.99		6	-100.43	218.87	2.59	0.20
+		-20.64		5	-104.48	222.97	6.69	0.03
+				4	-106.30	223.09	6.81	0.02
+	-106.91		+	11	-88.48	228.30	12.02	0.00
+			+	10	-95.90	233.80	17.52	0.00
+		-58.24	+	11	-94.28	239.90	23.62	0.00
+	-106.20	-1.39	+	12	-88.48	239.96	23.69	0.00
				2	-121.76	248.18	31.90	0.00
	-26.95			3	-121.53	250.48	34.20	0.00

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
		-13.70		3	-121.58	250.57	34.30	0.00
	-21.09	-9.38		4	-121.46	253.42	37.14	0.00
			+	8	-120.12	268.24	51.96	0.00
	74.71		+	9	-119.76	273.89	57.61	0.00
		55.29	+	9	-119.88	274.13	57.85	0.00
	60.20	20.65	+	10	-119.74	281.49	65.21	0.00

(H)

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
	-22.78			3	-60.54	129.47	0.00	0.32
		-12.88		3	-60.85	130.09	0.62	0.24
				2	-62.61	130.32	0.85	0.21
	-16.82	-8.59		4	-59.72	131.89	2.41	0.10
+	-23.41			4	-60.44	133.33	3.85	0.05
+				3	-62.61	133.62	4.14	0.04
+		-13.19		4	-60.77	133.99	4.52	0.03
+	-17.41	-8.86		5	-59.56	136.62	7.15	0.01
			+	8	-50.60	146.00	16.52	0.00
	-9.62		+	9	-50.50	164.00	34.53	0.00

breeding_stage	mean_boat	mean_spec	season	df	logLik	AICc	delta	weight
+			+	9	-50.57	164.13	34.66	0.00
		-2.80	+	9	-50.58	164.15	34.68	0.00
+	-20.34		+	10	-50.29	193.91	64.44	0.00
+		-6.60	+	10	-50.48	194.30	64.82	0.00
	-10.57	0.98	+	10	-50.50	194.33	64.86	0.00
+	-18.74	-2.41	+	11	-50.28	254.56	125.08	0.00

Supplementary table 3. Best model summary for (A) Daily number of spectators (n = 1342), (B) Daily number of vessels (n = 824), (C) Overlap among penguins (n = 110), (D) Overlap between penguins and marine traffic (n = 49), (E) Departure time relative to nautical dawn (n = 21), (F) Arrival time relative to nautical dusk (n = 21), (G) Mass gain per day at sea (n = 21), (H) Chick meal size (n = 14).

(A)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	1,134.43	19.46	1,328	< .001	-0.59	[-0.73, -0.46]
month [10]	88.50	2.01	1,328	.044	0.11	[0.00, 0.21]
month [11]	232.16	5.24	1,328	< .001	0.28	[0.18, 0.39]
month [12]	823.10	18.72	1,328	< .001	0.99	[0.89, 1.10]
year [2011]	18.64	0.26	1,328	.798	0.02	[-0.15, 0.20]
year [2012]	114.07	1.56	1,328	.118	0.14	[-0.03, 0.31]
year [2013]	215.03	2.95	1,328	.003	0.26	[0.09, 0.43]
year [2014]	292.11	4.01	1,328	< .001	0.35	[0.18, 0.53]
year [2015]	552.59	7.58	1,328	< .001	0.67	[0.49, 0.84]

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
year [2016]	656.29	9.00	1,328	< .001	0.79	[0.62, 0.97]
year [2017]	556.21	7.63	1,328	< .001	0.67	[0.50, 0.84]
year [2018]	601.84	8.26	1,328	< .001	0.73	[0.55, 0.90]
year [2019]	461.52	6.33	1,328	< .001	0.56	[0.38, 0.73]
year [2020]	-1,242.79	-17.05	1,328	< .001	-1.50	[-1.67, -1.33]

(B)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	206.42	26.85	814	< .001	-0.70	[-0.90, -0.50]
month [11]	15.69	2.16	814	.031	0.20	[0.02, 0.39]
month [12]	27.99	4.10	814	< .001	0.36	[0.19, 0.54]
month [9]	-22.46	-3.27	814	.001	-0.29	[-0.47, -0.12]
year [2015]	42.90	4.71	814	< .001	0.56	[0.33, 0.79]
year [2016]	49.94	5.49	814	< .001	0.65	[0.42, 0.88]
year [2017]	57.35	6.30	814	< .001	0.75	[0.51, 0.98]
year [2018]	84.89	9.33	814	< .001	1.10	[0.87, 1.33]
year [2019]	58.50	5.89	814	< .001	0.76	[0.51, 1.01]
year [2020]	50.61	5.56	814	< .001	0.66	[0.43, 0.89]

(C)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	0.51	3.86	29	< .001	0.51	[0.26, 0.77]
year A [2015]	1.23	5.98	29	< .001	1.23	[0.84, 1.65]
year A [2016]	0.24	1.79	29	.074	0.24	[-0.02, 0.51]
year A [2017]	0.32	2.30	29	.021	0.32	[0.05, 0.60]
year A [2018]	0.68	4.18	29	< .001	0.68	[0.37, 1.01]
year A [2019]	0.42	2.90	29	.004	0.42	[0.14, 0.71]
year A [2020]	0.23	1.67	29	.095	0.23	[-0.04, 0.49]
year B [2015]	1.23	5.98	29	< .001	1.23	[0.84, 1.65]
year B [2016]	0.24	1.79	29	.074	0.24	[-0.02, 0.51]
year B [2017]	0.32	2.30	29	.021	0.32	[0.05, 0.60]

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
year B [2018]	0.68	4.18	29	< .001	0.68	[0.37, 1.01]
year B [2019]	0.42	2.90	29	.004	0.42	[0.14, 0.71]
year B [2020]	0.23	1.67	29	.095	0.23	[-0.04, 0.49]

(D)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	6.68	12.45	42	< .001	6.68	[5.68, 7.78]
penguin year [2015]	40.61	10.59	42	< .001	40.61	[33.47, 48.52]
penguin year [2016]	-0.42	-0.58	42	.563	-0.42	[-1.87, 1.01]
penguin year [2017]	-3.88	-6.68	42	< .001	-3.88	[-5.07, -2.79]
penguin year [2018]	-5.14	-9.33	42	< .001	-5.14	[-6.27, -4.11]
penguin year [2019]	-2.00	-3.06	42	.002	-2.00	[-3.31, -0.74]
penguin year [2020]	-1.26	-1.82	42	.069	-1.26	[-2.63, 0.09]

(E)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	-74.94	-21.68	18	< .001	-1.17	[-1.53, -0.81]
breeding stage [Incubation]	43.16	8.83	18	< .001	2.13	[1.62, 2.64]

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
breeding stage [PG]	27.80	5.69	18	< .001	1.37	[0.87, 1.88]

(F)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	9.25	4.06	20	.001	-0.00	[-0.46, 0.46]

(G)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	302.43	24.05	17	< .001	0.87	[0.54, 1.19]
breeding stage [Incubation]	-173.21	-9.68	17	< .001	-2.12	[-2.58, -1.66]
breeding stage [PG]	-39.24	-2.20	17	.042	-0.48	[-0.94, -0.02]
mean boat	-56.86	-3.28	17	.004	-0.31	[-0.50, -0.11]

(H)

Parameter	<i>b</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	β	95% CI (β)
(Intercept)	273.45	51.12	12	< .001	-0.00	[-0.52, 0.52]
mean boat	-22.78	-2.04	12	.064	-0.51	[-1.05, 0.04]

Supplementary table 4. Stable isotopes samples distribution from 2010 to 2020

Breeding		sex	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
stage													
			22	20	13	13	20	14	19	20	19	20	17
Guard	F	9	9	1	3	7	8	9	11	10	10	10	8
	M	6	9	8		6	7	10	10	10	10	10	9
Incubation	F	9	10		7	9	11	12	11	9	10	10	9
	M	11	10		9	10	9	8	10	10	10	11	11
			20	20	20		14	19	20	23	9	19	18
Post-guard	F	9	6	2						9	4	9	9
	M	8	10	2						6	5	9	9

Supplementary figure 1. Evolution of the proportion of vessel types in the Bass strait marine traffic. Vessels types representing less than 0.5% of the dataset were merged in the “Other” type.

